

Sample Name: PVC UV <1 μm

Material: Polyvinyl Chloride

Size: <1 μm

Production Partner: TNO

Storage Conditions: Refrigerated and dark

Summary

Physical Characteristics

- Median diameter (D_{50_v}) = 1,93 μm
- Particles have an irregular morphology
- $1,1 \times 10^{13}$ particles per gram
- 43088 cm²/g surface area

Chemical Characteristics

- >99% C₂ClH₃ (PVC) determined by XRF
- C=O peak (1732 cm⁻¹) due to oxidation observed in FTIR spectrum
- Not able to obtain a cathodoluminescence spectrum

Description of terms

- D[4,3]: Volume mean (μm)
- D[3,2]: Surface area mean (μm)
- D[2,1]: Spherical particle mean (μm)
- D[1,0]: Number length mean (μm)
- D_{50_v}: Median diameter (volume basis, μm)
- D_{50_N}: Median diameter (number basis, μm)
- N_w: Number of particles per gram plastic (#/g)
- A_w: Surface area of particles per gram plastic (cm²/g)

Particle Size Distribution (using *Static Light Scattering (SLS)* provided by TNO)

D[4,3]	D[3,2]	D[2,1]	D[1,0]	D50 _N	D50 _V	N _w	A _w
2,33	1,22	0,47	0,26	0,20	1,93	1.1×10^{13}	43088

Chemical Composition (using XRF provided by Malvern Panalytical)

Chemical formula	Concentration (%)
C_2ClH_3	99,81
Element	Concentration (ppm)
Na	36
Al	443
Si	281
P	51
S	709
Ca	45
Cr	66
Fe	167
Ni	12
Cu	3
Zn	4
Mo	4

Chemical Bonding (Using μ -FTIR provided by TNO)Cathodoluminescence Spectroscopy (provided by TNO)

Not available